

Corsaren: Multimodal Storytelling in Nineteenth Century Danish Satire

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1 Introduction: Challenges of Satire

Among the many *Golden Age* designations for periods of European cultural flourishing, one of the lesser-known is the “golden age of caricature”. Originally applied to late eighteenth- and early nineteenth-century England and its prolific satirical print culture (Taylor 2018; Smith 2025), the term equally fits wider Western Europe. Rising popular journalism, higher literacy, new industrial print technologies (especially lithography), and expanding press freedoms created ideal conditions for illustrated satire to spread across the continent, including Denmark (Maidment 2017; Cuno 1994; St. Clair 2007; Koch et al. 1984; Kerr 2000; Maidment 2013; Potter 2019).

The Danish satirical weekly *Corsaren* (1840-1855), launched by Meir Goldschmidt (1819–1887), quickly became both widely read and politically feared (Ober 2001). Throughout its run, it operated against a political backdrop marked by tension between national-liberal constitutionalism and conservative absolutism. Around 1843, the journal moved from overt political engagement toward culturally focused satire, targeting figures such as Heiberg and Kierkegaard, before drifting toward pure entertainment by the mid-1840s (Nygaard 2022).

Each issue of the *Corsaren* features written critique and satirical illustrations, which sometimes take up the majority of the page. Meaning rarely resides in text or image alone: it emerges from their interaction and tension. To understand the *Corsaren*’s storytelling, it must be approached as a complex medium that used a distinct, multimodal grammar to convey its narrative (Maziarczyk 2011).

Multimodality and narratology are both familiar topics in the field of Digital Humanities. Whereas narratology is often a subject of inquiry, such as in Computational Literary Studies (Flüh et al. 2021), multimodality is usually associated with Vision Language Models (Smits and Wevers 2023) or multimodal media. Nandy et al. 2024’s multimodal approach to caricatures, for instance, encompasses benchmarking vision language models in their understanding of visual satire through prompting.

Our approach differs from those studies by not focusing on the combination of text and image within the models, but their interplay within the narrative structures of *Corsaren*, handling them as a phenomenon of intermediality in a narrow sense, meaning they encompass a multimodal interaction between text and image (Rippl

2014, 143; on the complementary relationship between multimodality and intermediality see Jensen and Schirrmacher 2024). Graphical satire has been addressed within this framework before, for instance by Bricker 2022. He demonstrates how the intermedial combination of text and image in satire leads to “dialectical cycles of readerly re-interpretation”, leading to a meaning making through “re-semantification”: an iterative process in which the interpretation of one medium (image) might lead to a re-interpretation of another (text).

Compared to media with a stronger coherent narrative, satire usually tells a story on its own while also mirroring contemporary (political) events, which adds to the challenge of computational analysis. *Corsaren* is part of a discourse – both in its text and visual references.

The main challenges are:

- **Linguistic:** How is language used to represent a political standpoint in satire?
- **Contextual:** Satire exposes gaps between reality and ideals through humor and critique (Sterling 2009). Grasping *Corsaren*’s content therefore requires grounding the analysis in historical events and in Goldschmidt’s personal relations and opinions, supported by ongoing “qualitative checks”.
- **Discursive:** The narrative is not confined to *Corsaren* but spans other newspapers, letters, and reviews. We must therefore recognize that *Corsaren* does not paint the whole picture and anticipate gaps in the broader discourse.
- **Visual:** Images depict both contemporary individuals as caricatures and abstract concepts, e.g., nations, citizens, and politics. Such tensions between form and meaning need to be considered in image clustering.
- **Multimodal:** The correlation of textual and visual phenomena is an act of (computational) re-contextualization, which demands a proper framework. A computational return to true multimodality remains a major challenge due to the complexity of the semantic modes and their interactions (Hiippala 2021).

Addressing all these challenges is an ambitious task that cannot be solved in a single study. Here, we take two initial steps toward anchoring image and text in *Corsaren* to understand how satire is conveyed, while remaining mindful of these broader issues.

2 Corpus and Methods

Our corpus includes 211 editions of *Corsaren* (2,832 articles, 1840–1844). The almost-weekly issues averaged eight pages, and the share of illustrations – after a small early increase – stabilized at about 50% from 1842–1843 onward (see Figure 1). Due to the low OCR quality, we use a re-digitized sample from the *Enevældens Nyheder Online* (ENO) project at Aalborg University (Heinsen and Bøgeskov 2025).¹ Articles are enriched with semantic embeddings generated with the `Old_News_Segmentation_SBERT_V0.1`

¹Full ENO corpus: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/JohanHeinsen/ENO>.

Figure 1: Page of *Corsaren*, edition of 13 September, 1844.

model, a Sentence Transformers model trained for article segmentation of the ENO corpus.² Images are segmented with the NewNa-Segmentation tool (Kreten and Göke 2025), a semi-automatic implementation of the Newspaper Navigator (Lee and Weld 2020). We segmented 5,494 images in total; 972 are from the period 1840–1844, the remaining 4,522 are from the period 1844–1853 (we don’t have high quality OCR-ed text from this period yet).

We propose the following methods for the first steps towards anchoring image and text in *Corsaren*:

- **Lexical and semantic analysis of *Corsaren*’s text.** We perform a classification task with a logistic regression to distinguish satirical from non-satirical text, using TF-IDF representations and semantic embeddings as features. As a reference corpus, we use *National news* articles from contemporary non-satirical newspapers in the same ENO corpus (see Table 1). The model’s performance metrics indicate the strength of lexical and semantic differences between *Cor-*

²See https://huggingface.co/JohanHeinsen/Old_News_Segmentation_SBERT_V0.1. This model achieved the best results in benchmark evaluations of Danish and multilingual language models on historical Danish newspapers (Lassche et al. 2026).

Corpus	Newspaper	Editions	(<i>National news</i> *) articles	Words
Satirical	<i>Corsaren</i>	211	2,832	856,600
Non-satirical	<i>Aalborg Stiftstidende</i>	1,311	27,374	3,233,217
	<i>Aarhuus Stifts-Tidende</i>	1,124	22,140	2,596,583
	<i>Den Nord-Cimbriske Tilskuer</i>	743	12,916	1,352,758
	<i>Lolland-Falsters Stifts-Tidende</i>	765	12,678	2,090,909
	<i>Ribe Stifts Adresseavisen</i>	673	12,856	1,523,697
	<i>Viborger Samler</i>	1034	21,807	2,510,339

Table 1: Descriptive statistics on the newspapers in the ‘Satirical’ and ‘Non-satirical’ corpus for the period 1840-1844. The articles have been labeled by category (*National news*, *International news*, *Advertisement*, and *Miscellaneous*). This was done with a LogisticRegression model that took the Old_News embeddings as input. F1-scores of the categories were > 0.9 . *This only applies to the newspapers from the ‘Non-satirical’ corpus.

saren articles and common news reporting. Error analysis and inspection of feature contributions will help us further clarify these differences.

- **Exploration of *Corsaren*’s illustrations.** After manually correcting the image segmentation, we extract image embeddings with EVA-02-CLIP. We use the embeddings for (1) an exploration of the feature space regarding its representativeness for caricaturizing effects using KNN and UMAP and (2) an investigation of textual prompts pertaining to known strategies of visual satire (distortions of the face, for example).

3 Preliminary Results

Table 2 contains the performance metrics of our first text classification tasks. The high scores indicate strong lexical and semantic differences between *Corsaren* articles and non-satirical news. As the SHAP summary plot of the TF-IDF features in Figure 2 shows, the pronouns *vi* (we), *jeg* (I) and *du* (you) strongly characterize satirical text, underscoring the opinionated and subjective tone of *Corsaren*.

A first insight into the images reveals how the model is not only able to pick up on the motif and content, such as animals or humans in different poses and constellations, but also caricaturing effects such as anthropomorphized figures (Figure 3) and distortions in the face (Figure 3). This allows us to study the occurrence, spectra and use of these visual effects in more detail and in correlation to the textual phenomena.

Figure 2: SHAP summary plot of the fifty most influential TF-IDF n-gram features in the satire classifier ($ngram_range = (1, 3)$). Points represent each feature’s contribution (SHAP value) to individual predictions, with colours indicating the feature’s TF-IDF magnitude. Positive values push the model towards predicting satire, negative values towards non-satire. Features are ranked by their average absolute impact on the model’s decisions.

Features	Precision		Recall		F1-score	
	<i>satirical</i>	<i>non-satirical</i>	<i>satirical</i>	<i>non-satirical</i>	<i>satirical</i>	<i>non-satirical</i>
TF-IDF	0.914 ± 0.011	0.917 ± 0.014	0.917 ± 0.015	0.914 ± 0.012	0.916 ± 0.001	0.915 ± 0.010
embeddings	0.931 ± 0.011	0.949 ± 0.009	0.950 ± 0.009	0.929 ± 0.012	0.940 ± 0.007	0.939 ± 0.008

Table 2: Performance of LogisticRegression models with TF-IDF representations (*ngram_range* = (1,3)) and semantic embeddings as features. The dataset is down-sampled to have balanced classes (2,832 data points per class, with 415 data points from each non-satirical newspaper). The model is trained across fifty iterations, reserving 20% for testing in each run.

Figure 3: KNN explorer with an image cluster of anthropomorphized figures resembling different types of birds. This demonstrates CLIPS out-of-the-box capability of identifying specific human-animal-hybrids, which are frequently used in the Cor-saren.

Figure 4: CLIP text search with the prompt "mouth caricature", resulting in figures with distortions of this specific facial feature.

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